

Research

Water Quality Assessment of the Betkot Lake, Sudurpaschim Province, Nepal

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Abstract Wetlands are the most productive ecosystems in the world, and are also considered as the kidney of nature. The lentic environments i.e., lake, and ponds are the inland water bodies, not only provides the water but also supports the livelihood, habitat of plants and animals, regulates the hydrological cycle, and aesthetic values including other environmental services. The study on the hydrochemistry of the lentic ecosystems will have immense significance in updating the existing environmental and chemical database and also support to maintain their ecological health. The Betkot Lake, located in the Kanchanpur district, of Sudurpaschim Province, Nepal plays a key role in the ecology of the lowland Terai region and the present study emphasized on the hydrochemical assessment of its water quality. Besides ecological importance, the water body have a significant role in irrigation, fisheries, power generation and domestic water use. Recently, the lake has been witnessing severe deterioration in water quality mainly due to anthropogenic activities. For further assessment we had collected altogether 13 water samples in winter season, 2018, and the parameters of water temperature, pH, EC, TDS, DO, turbidity, free CO₂, major cations, and anions including alkalinity, phosphate, ammonia, hardness, BOD and COD were analyzed. The results revealed that the water quality meets the guideline of Nepal's Drinking Water Quality; however, some parameters like concentrations of DO, BOD, COD and ammonia didn't meet the Nepal Water Quality Guidelines for Aqua Culture in some of the sampling locations. In addition to the

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usual interactions of Lake Environment with the fragile local land topography, the lake is subjected to anthropogenic interference due to its proximity to the increasing settlements and mobility of people around the lake. Multivariate statistical methods i.e., Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (CA) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) were applied to assess the influence of pollutants disposal and their controlling mechanism. Particularly, the PCA results demonstrated that both natural and anthropogenic factors contributing to the contamination in the lake with 87.37 % cumulative variance. On the other hand, the CA results differentiate the sampling locations into four clusters and the pollution index level indicated that the all the sites are slightly polluted. Meanwhile, the quantitative pollution level exhibited in different clustering sites by using Pollution Index that indicated the outlet area was relatively more polluted than inlet sides.

Keywords: *Lentic environments, Physicochemical properties, Water quality, Pollution index, Multivariate statistical analysis*

1. Introduction

Water quality is considered the main factor controlling health and the state of disease in all aspects of living organism. However, surface water quality is often subjected to contamination since it is uncovered and easily accessible. Thus, pollution as a primary problematic in surface water issue that is largely controlled by natural processes i.e., weathering and soil erosion and anthropogenic inputs including municipal and industrial wastewater discharge (Pant *et al.*, 2018). The anthropogenic discharges constitute a constant polluting source, whereas surface runoff is a seasonal phenomenon mostly affected by climate within the basin (Singh *et al.*, 2004, Singh *et al.*, 2005). The lentic environments are closed water bodies that lack the natural purification and resilience like lotic water bodies, and the quality of the lake water is essential in maintaining the healthy lake ecosystem. It can be assessed with the help of physicochemical parameters and biological components of water. The alteration of physicochemical properties may harm the biodiversity and ecosystem of the lentic environments, as well as human beings (Neupane *et al.*, 2010). The lake ecosystems which not only provides the water but also supports the livelihood, habitat of plants and animals, regulates the hydrological cycle and has aesthetic values (Gitelson *et al.*, 1993). The lakes are the main sinks which has dissolved and particulate organic and inorganic compounds and gases, that produced by both natural as well as anthropogenic activities, and adversely affecting the human and ecological health of the environments. In recent years, CA and PCA are gradually accepted and applied to improve the efficiency of the long-term monitoring of the water quality, as the conclusions of this multivariate analysis are consistent with each other and also support the previous studies on the statistical basis. This showed that change use of land and the

anthropogenic intervention can change the water quality parameters of water bodies like lake; however, these changes are not significant while comparing the concentration's hydrochemical parameters between the sampling sites.

In Nepal, wetlands cover over 743,500 hectares of area, i.e. nearly 5% of the total area of the country, and among them Terai consists of large numbers of wetlands (163) followed by hills and the mountains (79). Sudurpaschim Province, lies in the western part, has the highest number of wetland areas in Nepal especially in the lowland Terai region i.e., Kanchanpur and Kailali districts. Some of the potential lakes in these two districts are: Ramaroshan Lake Complex (complex stands for a cluster of lakes), Ghodagodi Lake Complex, Jhokar Lake, Jhilmila Lake, Betkot Lake etc. The region is divided into two hydrologic units: The Upper and Lower Basins, and both the basins are connected at the mid-hills and Churiya ranges. The lakes are experiencing pollution, encroachment, eutrophication, and over utilization in Nepal (Kafle *et al.*, 2008) so as in Sudurpaschim Province the lakes are being polluted due to several natural and anthropogenic activities. Beside the influx of sediments from the lake catchment due to erosion, runoff, discharge of untreated sewage and industrial waste waters and solid waste, climate change, over-exploitation of lake for other activities disturb the lake ecosystem and its water quality (Pant, 2013). The lake of Kanchanpur districts are not the exception of it.

The Betkot Lake lies in Kanchanpur District and has religious importance with famous religious places including Baijanath Temple located in the periphery of lake. Despite of having the aesthetic values, the lake is facing several types of threats including anthropogenic activities and natural hydraulic dynamics like flash flood, debris from the under construction road and local activities like grazing, forage and fodder, firewood etc. alters the quality of water. Such type of dependency on Lake Site resources has depleted the natural condition of lake (Neupane *et al.*, 2010). In addition, the religious and touristic activities are also leading towards the organic and other pollutants (Neupane *et al.*, 2010). The rapid urbanizations, migrations, haphazard settlement and unmanaged developmental activities are heavily increasing in the region. Hence, water pollution in the lake became a common visible criterion and it has been exaggerated in last few decades, primarily because of population growth and the changing climatic conditions. Since the study of lake environment in the lowland regions of Nepal is very limited and those a few were reported from eastern and central regions. In these regions also, the primary data base studies were very few focusing on lake environments. Therefore, there is the need to determine the aspects of pollutions as well as their levels for the academic

research, policy and other perspectives. Nevertheless, the wetlands have been given little attention by decision makers in all the sectors including Local, Provincial and Federal Governmental levels. Thus, present study aimed to evaluate the water quality of the Betkot Lake based on physiochemical parameters.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

Betkot Lake (Fig. 1) covering ~5 ha with a maximum depth of 11 m (Neupane et al., 2010) is situated at 29° 01'36" N latitude and 80° 19'14" E in 482 m altitude of Churiya Hills, Sudurpaschim Province, Nepal. The lake is about 7 km away from the human settlement and ~13 km far from the head quarter of Kanchanpur district i.e. Mahendranagar. The surrounding area of the lake is covered by the forest of *Mallotus* and *Shorea species*. It has historical value as well as a religious place as thousands of Hindu pilgrim from Nepal, India and other countries visit each year for worship.

Figure 1 (a): Location map of the Betkot Lake

(b): Sampling locations in the Betkot Lake

2.2. Sampling and analysis

The water samples were collected in the month of November 2018, a transitional period of summer and winter. Altogether, 13 purposive samples were collected from the Betkot Lake along the periphery of Lake (Table 1 a & b). The sites were selected which represent maximum area of lake with the inlet, outlet and change in the land use. The physicochemical parameters such as temperature, pH, EC, TDS, turbidity, dissolved oxygen (DO) were measured in field using the multi-parameter instrument HANNA and DO by DO meter along with turbidity by turbidity meter onsite. While total hardness (TH), calcium hardness (CaH), magnesium hardness (MgH), free carbon di-oxide (CO₂), potassium (K⁺), sodium (Na⁺), calcium (Ca²⁺), magnesium (Mg²⁺), ammonia (NH₄⁺), nitrate (NO₃⁻), phosphate (PO₄³⁻), chloride (Cl⁻), alkalinity, chemical oxygen demand (COD), and biological oxygen demand (BOD) were analyzed in laboratory of the Central Department of Environmental Science, under the Institute of Science and Technology, Tribhuvan University (CDES-TU).

Water sample collection and analytical procedure following by APHA (1998); Temperature in °C, EC μS/cm and all other parameters are in mg/L except pH. The sample were kept in 2 L polyethylene plastic bottle which were previously cleaned with metal free shop, rinsed repeatedly with distilled water, soaked in 10% nitric acid for 24 hours. All water samples were maintained 4°C before they reach the laboratory. For the further analysis, the

standard method prescribes by the APHA (1998) were used in this study. The data was analyzed with the help of MS Excel 2013 and SPSS version 21. In addition, the data was analyzed using multivariate technique such as principal component (PCA) and cluster analysis (CA) to evaluate the information about the similarities and controlling mechanisms. In addition, level of pollution at particular location among the different sampling site were ascertained by using the pollution index (PI).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 General Hydrochemistry

Surface water temperature of the natural lentic and lotic water bodies vary in daily and seasonal basis due to different environmental factors. Furthermore, it also varies within a daytime, weather, terrain, slope and aspects, and source region temperature of recharge water for instance inlets and groundwater. In the lentic environments, the temperature is one of the important parameters that affect the chemistry and biological reactions in the water (Trivedi and Goel, 1986) as well as pollution and the subsequent chemical reactions may affect lake water temperature. In addition, the temperature also plays a significant role for aquatic environment that regulates physicochemical and biological activities in the different layers of the lakes for instance littoral, limnetic and profundal, and responsible for the mixing of water with varieties of the nutrients. Nevertheless, the water temperature in the lentic environments, determine the growth rate of aquatic plants and algae, and their interactions with many aquatic animals. A higher temperature has depleted solubility of DO in water, and reduced the concentrations of DO. The warmer water obviously accelerates the decay of organic matter contents in the river. The temperature of the Betkot lake water is moderate (ranging from 17.10 to 19.70°C; Table 1 and 2) which is identical to the regional temperature of the lowland areas during the month of October-November and this temperature was found to be suitable for the various chemical and biological functioning in the lake.

The pH is a measure of the acidity or alkalinity of water, expressed in terms of its concentration of hydrogen ions (APHA, 1998). It has a major role in both lentic and lotic environments for determining the speciation of inorganic chemicals and influencing the biotic life. Generally, pH value 6.5 to 8.5 is suitable for the growth and development of the aquatic plants. It's values usually changed by the presence of organic and inorganic solutes together with reaction of carbon dioxide and the higher pH leads to the precipitation of the heavy metals

(ionic species) to the soil and sediments in the lentic environments. Photosynthesis uses up dissolved carbon dioxide, which acts like carbonic acid (H_2CO_3) in water. Removal of CO_2 reduces the acidity of the water resulting the increment of pH and in lake; the respiration of organic matter produces CO_2 , which dissolves in water as carbonic acid, thereby lowering the pH. Hence, pH may be higher during daylight hours and the growing season, when photosynthesis is at a maximum peak. The pH may change with depth in a lake, due again to changes in photosynthesis and other chemical reactions. There is typically a seasonal decrease in pH in the lower layers of a stratified lake because of CO_2 accumulation. The pH of the lake ranges from 7.44 to 8.10, indicating the mildly alkaline conditions (Table 1 and 2). Irrespective of the different locations, the pH values of the lake vary minimum, and it remains almost neutral in most of the sampling locations.

Table 1: Onsite measured parameters according to sampling site locations

S.N.	Sites	Latitude (N)	Longitude (E)	Tem.	pH	EC	TDS	Tur.	DO
1	Site 1	29°01'24.05"	80°19'07.67"	19.00	7.90	338	168	8.20	3.02
2	Site 2	29°01'25.85"	80°19'08.31"	18.80	7.79	325	162	11.20	2.98
3	Site 3	29°01'27.67"	80°19'08.97"	18.50	7.73	326	164	11.50	2.97
4	Site 4	29°01'28.27"	80°19'11.45"	18.50	7.67	325	163	10.10	3.43
5	Site 5	29°01'29.07"	80°29'13.78"	18.40	7.63	331	164	14.20	3.16
6	Site 6	29°01'27.78"	80°19'15.85"	18.60	7.66	352	176	8.30	2.72
7	Site 7	29°01'26.91"	80°19'29.14"	19.70	7.44	396	199	7.50	2.25
8	Site 8	29°01'24.69"	80°19'18.19"	18.40	7.60	336	170	10.20	3.24
9	Site 9	29°01'23.03"	80°19'16.09"	18.00	7.71	326	163	7.40	3.89
10	Site 10	29°01'21.94"	80°19'14.29"	17.70	7.87	329	164	8.10	2.81
11	Site 11	29°01'21.96"	80°19'12.37"	17.10	7.92	323	162	8.50	2.82
12	Site 12	29°01'22.36"	80°19'10.05"	17.60	8.10	355	162	20.20	2.78
13	Site 13	29°01'22.19"	80°19'09.16"	17.60	8.04	324	162	12.60	2.70

Tem: Water temperature, EC: Electrical conductivity, TDS; Total dissolved solids, Tur: Turbidity, DO: Dissolved oxygen

The degree of mineralization, expressing as EC is measure by the total dissolved solids and ionized species in the waters, and it qualitatively reflects the status of inorganic pollution. Principally the EC is a measurement of ionic strength and it depends on the presence of ions, its concentrations, mobility and temperature. Other several factors determine the EC in the lentic environments such as temperature, ionic strength etc. Especially, the temperature in the lake waters have a significant proportional relation with the EC values as if the EC values of water increases by 2-3%, that resulted an increase of 1°C lake water temperature. Similarly, the TDS is also a good indicator of EC concentrations, as it increases with increasing TDS in the lakes. The ionic strength and inorganic pollution in the water also have a similar relation as temperature and TDS. In addition to aforementioned factors, the other local environmental factors such as aridity increases the EC values as evaporation takes place from the surface of water then the concentration of dissolved solid in the remaining water increases that leads to the increase in conductivity. In the present study, the EC shows comparatively considerable variability among the sampling locations, i.e., 323-396 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (Table 1 and 2) possibly due to the higher temperature, inorganic pollution, and ionic strength etc., but still within the range of WHO recommended standards.

The major ions, salts minerals are present in fresh surface water. These remains in dissolve condition from various sources such as runoff, waste water, stormflow and urban runoff, which contribute in TDS (Kent and Belitz, 2004). Thus, the concentration of TDS values are the indicators of erosion rate in the lentic environments. The excess TDS are natural or anthropogenic pollutants in the water and imparts the color, total alkalinity and conducting nature of water and increase increases the risk for the cultivated land as well as aquatic lives. Primary causes of higher TDS in the river water possibly due to rock weathering, agricultural runoff, discharge of domestic waste from the town and other human activities. TDS is directly related to salts concentrations and it can be calculated with the help of EC values using the following calculation:

$$\text{TDS (mg/L)} = 0.64 \times \text{EC } (\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}) \quad (1)$$

Nevertheless, when the salt concentration reaches a certain level, EC is no longer directly related to salts concentrations. It is therefore, similar to EC, TDS also exhibits relatively high values i.e., 162-199 mg/L in the present study.

However, the TDS results are within the range of standard limits. The literature revealed that the natural lakes in the world has TDS values less than 500 mg/L, the exceptions are also

found from the different areas of either from pollution (i.e., anthropogenic interferences), aridity or saline nature of underlying lithology. However, previous studies showed that a majority of Himalayan freshwater bodies have TDS values relatively very low (< 100 mg/L (Pant et al., 2018). In the present study, the TDS ranges from 162-199 mg/L with mean concentrations of 168 mg/L. The calculated value of TDS using Eq (1) is 215 mg/L, which is slightly higher than the actual measurements while the concentrations of all the sampling sites were within the range of standard values. Turbidity is an optical characteristic of water and is a measurement of the amount of light scattered by material in the water when a light is shined through the water sample. Higher the intensity of scattered light, the higher the turbidity. Material that causes water to be turbid include clay, silt, very tiny inorganic and organic matter, algae, dissolved colored organic compounds, and plankton and other microscopic organisms. In addition, the effluent and waste including added sewage to the lakes increases turbidity as any surface run off carrying soil or particles from the land. Generally, in the freshwater lentic environments, the clear green color, and turbidities are low, usually less than 10 NTU. In the present study, the turbidity is relatively high and it varies from 7.40-20.20 NTU, which is more than the WHO limit possibly due to the lower intensity of the light as the area is covered by dense forest.

DO is one of the key factors in determining the health of the lentic environments. Generally, a minimum oxygen concentration of needed for cold-water and warm water fishes is 7 mg/L and 5 mg/L respectively. Oxygen can enter a lake via three different routes. The main mechanism is atmospheric diffusion where oxygen in the air is absorbed by surface water due to a difference in oxygen concentrations. Second, aquatic plants photosynthesize and release oxygen into the water. The third one is the inlet sources i.e. rivers and streams bring oxygenated water into the lake. Once DO levels drop below to 2 mg/L, the water is described as hypoxic and still drop to 0 mg/L, it becomes anoxic. A dead zone is an area within a lake that is either hypoxic or anoxic, and in this condition, very few organisms can survive and most of the oxygen consuming organisms either suffocate or leave the area. The DO concentrations are constantly affected by diffusion and aeration, photosynthesis, respiration and decomposition. While water equilibrates toward 100% air saturation, DO levels will also fluctuate with temperature, and pressure changes. The DO concentrations may decrease while increasing the depth of the lake. In this study, the DO concentrations were recorded onsite that ranges from 2.25-3.89 mg/L. The level of oxygen in the lake was reported very low (< 6 mg/L) it is due to the low light and high organic load in the lake environment. As stated in UNESCO-IUCN,

2005, the concentrations of DO below 3.00 mg/L are likely fatal to freshwater fish, and the present study dataset is lower than the NWQGAC guideline too.

The concentration of different hydrochemical parameters and major ions were determined through the field as well as lab measurements, and they indicate the various chemical relationships to each other. The ionic relations, basically the major cations and anions indicated hydrochemistry of the lentic waters and regulated by various hydrochemical reactions. The chemical rock weathering (calcite, dolomite, feldspar of Na and K, Ca-plagioclase) and evaporite dissolution (halite, anhydrite and gypsum) yield different combinations of dissolved ions which play vital role in controlling the hydro geochemistry of the water are given in equation 2-9.

The major ions, for instance Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} primarily originate from the weathering of carbonates, silicates and evaporites, Na^+ and K^+ from the dissolution of evaporites and weathering of silicates and Cl^- from the evaporites dissolution. In addition, alkalinity predominantly derived from the weathering of carbonate and silicates minerals (Eq: 2-7), whereas Cl^- is mainly derived from the halite (Eq: 9; Mortatti and Probst, 2003; Thomas et al., 2015). Thus, all these ionic relations indicated that hydrochemistry of the water is mainly regulated by carbonate weathering with evaporites dissolution followed by minor contribution

of silicate weathering. The water quality determines by the hardness of water and it depends on the present of dissolved minerals. Calcium and magnesium are among the most common ingredients found in natural waters and their salts are an important contributor to the hardness of water. Thus, the total hardness (TH) in water is due to the sum of concentrations of alkaline earth metal ions such as Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} . The TH is the total water-soluble calcium and magnesium salt present water expressed as its CaCO_3 equivalent. Total hardness includes bicarbonates, chlorides and sulphates of calcium and magnesium etc. The present study showed that the total hardness ranged from 178-200 mg/L with an average value of the 188 mg/L, which is relatively lower than the previous results conducted by Neupane et al. (2010). This decreased value of TH possibly due to the seasonal variations and different anthropogenic interferences in the different times. Free carbon dioxide is present in water in the form of a dissolved gas. Surface of the lentic environments normally contains about 10 mg/ L free CO_2 . The free CO_2 is readily soluble in water and calcium and magnesium combine with carbon dioxide to form carbonates and bicarbonates. The life of aquatic flora directly depends upon CO_2 in lentic water for growth as an example the phytoplankton utilize CO_2 in the photosynthesis of plant materials; starches, sugars, oils, proteins. Not only floral, but also faunal life also indirectly depends on the CO_2 present in the water. The carbon in all these materials comes from the CO_2 in lake water. For instance, when the oxygen concentration in water containing organic matter is reduced, the carbon dioxide concentration rises. The rise in carbon dioxide makes it more difficult for the lentic fauna (e.g., fish) to use the limited amount of available oxygen. In the present study, the free CO_2 values ranges from 4.60-10.50 mg/L, with mean concentrations of 7.32 mg/L. The value of CO_2 in the lake was found within the range of standard limit.

The hydrochemistry of the lake environment is mainly determined by the presence of major ions (e.g., Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} and alkalinity) (Zinabu *et al.*, 2002). On the basis of mean value (mg/L) concentration, the dominance of major cations shows the following increment pattern: $\text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{NH}_4^+$. This shows Ca^{2+} alone contributes about 54.9%, and remaining 45.1 % from Mg^{2+} (18.1%) Na^+ (16.9%) and K^+ (10.1%) with very negligible share of the NH_4^+ in the cationic budget. Among the measured anions, the contributions of alkalinity are 77.71%, followed by Cl^- (16.56%), NO_3^- (5.51%) and PO_4^{3-} (0.21%). BOD is a measurement of the amount of oxygen required to remove waste organic matter from water during decomposition by aerobic bacteria. The living bacterial organisms in lentic environment, plays a key role in stabilization or made unobjectionable of waste organic matter. The role of organic matter contents and the concentration of DO in the

lentic environment is integral to water-quality management which determine the level of BOD. Thus, BOD is an index of the degree of organic pollution in the lake water. Similarly, COD measure the oxygen consumption capacity of water during the decomposition of organic matter and the oxidation of inorganic chemicals such as ammonia and nitrite. The COD measurements are commonly made on waste waters samples or natural waters contaminated by domestic or industrial wastes. A commonly used oxidant in COD assays is potassium dichromate ($K_2Cr_2O_7$) which is used in combination with sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4). In the present study the concentration of BOD and COD were found to be 31.8 mg/L and 95.30 mg/L, respectively which is higher than guideline for aqua-culture. It indicates the low DO for the aquatic organisms which become stressed suffocate and die and sources of BOD include leaves and woody debris, dead plants and animals and its manure.

Table 2: Summary of hydrochemical parameters of the Betkot Lake (Value of temperature is expressed in °C, EC in $\mu S/cm$, turbidity in NTU and Other parameters in mg/L)

S.N.	Parameters	Min	Max	Mean	SD
1	Temperature	17.10	19.70	18.30	0.69
2	pH	7.44	8.10	7.77	0.19
3	EC	323.00	396.00	337	20.46
4	TDS	162.00	199.00	168	10.28
5	Turbidity	7.40	20.20	10.62	3.56
6	DO	2.25	3.89	2.98	0.40
7	TH	178.00	200.00	188.00	9.80
8	CaH	138.00	168.00	152.77	7.68
9	MgH	24.00	58.00	35.23	11.39
10	CO ₂	4.60	10.50	7.32	1.87
11	K ⁺	1.90	3.90	2.90	0.42
12	Na ⁺	4.46	5.49	4.89	0.33
13	Ca ²⁺	11.60	18.00	15.80	1.48
14	Mg ²⁺	5.15	8.30	6.80	0.98
15	NH ₄ ⁺	0.03	0.70	0.37	0.23
16	NO ₃ ⁻	0.60	3.46	1.77	0.71
17	PO ₄ ³⁻	0.06	0.07	0.07	0.00
18	Cl ⁻	2.78	9.94	5.31	2.42
19	Alkalinity	20.00	29.50	24.92	2.56
20	COD	50.84	115.94	95.38	21.06
21	BOD	16.95	38.65	31.80	7.02

3.2 Multivariate Statistical Analysis

3.2.1 Hierarchical Cluster Analysis

Hierarchical clustering is commonly applied to calculate the relationship of a single sample with the entire dataset, and is illustrated by a dendrogram (McKenna Jr, 2003). Thus, with cluster analysis, the similarity groups among the sample's sites. In previous studies, this approach was also used to determine the spatial variance of water quality parameters (Pant et al., 2018, Simeonov *et al.*, 2003). In the present study, Ward's method is used for clustering 13 sampling locations on the basis of the major ions (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Cl^- , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} , and alkalinity). All 13 sampling sites within the lake are grouped into four main clusters resulting in a dendrogram with low distance criterion between 0 and 5. Cluster 1 formed by 7 sampling sites (3, 4, 8-11 and 13) out of 13 which shows the influence of matter received from relatively less disturbance sites. The sites having a direct human disturbance formed Cluster 2 in which sites 1, 2 and 5 lies just near to the temple and road. The rest of sampling sites 6 and 12 formed Cluster 3 where these sites are noticed with algal blooms whereas in the 4th cluster has only one site (site 7) is located at the high level of anthropogenic activities, hence the high pollution in the site.

While interpreting clusters on the basis of TDS dataset results, the mean TDS (mg/L) is in the order of cluster 4 > 3 > 2 > 1 (i.e., 199 > 169 > 165 > 141). There is only one sampling point in the cluster 4 (i.e., location 7) with the highest TDS among the four clusters. The sampling locations of 3, 4, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 13 have relatively low TDS are corresponded to cluster 1. Site 1, 2 and 5 are located in the north-west positions have moderate mean TDS value are grouped into cluster 2. The clustering of these sites in same group could be due to the low pollution level in almost all the sites. Particularly, the mean value of cluster 3 (site: 6 and 12) was slightly higher than the cluster 2 and located in between cluster 2 and 4. The site 7 (cluster 4) is located at the inlet of the lake with relatively high anthropogenic activities including religious and other touristic spots. In addition, the possible reason is that sampling sites of cluster 4 are surrounded by cultivated land and affected by serious agricultural pollution. Similar results can be found in previous research on the hydrochemical studies from the Gandaki River, Indus River, Tigris River (Pant et al., 2018, Qaisar *et al.*, 2018) in which, the sites receiving pollutant discharge from the major natural or/and anthropogenic activities clustered in one group and moderately impacted sites were clustered in another. Interestingly, the classification results of CA do not exactly coincide with the distribution of the sites in

according to the locations; this could be due to the site-specific pollution along the bank of the lake environments. With the CA results, the sampling sites for further study can be reduced by designing a reasonable and optimal spatial sampling strategy in the lake.

Figure 2: Cluster analysis on the basis of site

3.2.2 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

The principal component analysis provides information on the most meaningful parameters which describe complete dataset allowing data reduction with minimum loss of original information (Helena *et al.*, 2000, Singh *et al.*, 2005). To identify the important water quality parameters and their controlling mechanisms, PCA is executed on 15 variables including EC, TDS, DO, major ions (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Cl^- , NO_3^- , and PO_4^{3-}), alkalinity, BOD and COD of the 13 different sampling sites which shows the major variables governing water physiochemical properties of the Betkot Lake. Principal components (PCs) with an eigenvalue over 1, are selected for further analyses (Fig. 3). The PCA results of the selected variables are presented in Table 3, and it indicates the leading PCs with loading values for each parameter. The loading values are classified according to Liu *et al.* (2003); the absolute loading values of > 0.75 , $0.75-0.50$, and $0.50-0.30$ are classified as strong, moderate, and weak, respectively. In winter, PC 1 accounts for 37.07% of the total variance with a strong positive loading values on DO, whereas, Cl^- has strong negatively loading values on BOD, and COD. This PC represents the effects of organic pollution in the lentic environment. It is very convincing associations that the state of DO and, BOD and COD has always inverse relations. PC2 accounts for 20.15% of the total variance and mainly represents the strong loading on EC

and TDS, and moderate negatively loading on NH_4^+ . Since, EC and TDS have direct relations with each other as mentioned in Eq (1), and contributions of NH_4^+ in the ionic load is negligible. Thus, these findings are also very considerable and in good agreement with the previous study (Pant et al., 2018). PC 3 accounts for 13.02% of the total variance and has strong positive loadings on Ca^{2+} , and Na^+ , and moderately positive loading on NH_4^+ , and PO_4^{3-} , indicating that they have similar sources. Similarly, in PC 4, explaining about 9.26% of the total variance, has strong positive loadings on Mg^{2+} , and NO_3^- indicating that though the underlying geological formation could be carbonate dominated lithology, but the source of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} are not same. Finally, in the PC 5, strong positive loading on TH, moderately positive loading on PO_4^{3-} further indicates that besides Ca^{2+} from PC 3 and Mg^{2+} from PC 4, other ions are responsible for the determinations of hardness in the lentic environments. Factor loading plot of PCs (Fig.3) also has a good agreement with the aforementioned explanations that Ca^{2+} , Na^+ , BOD and COD have some sort of linkage, where EC and TDS are closely associated with each other. On the other hand, Cl^- , NO_3^- , and DO have diverse sources while K^+ , Mg^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} have some linkage with each other.

Figure 3: Factor loading plot of the principal component analysis

3.3.3. Comprehensive pollution index (P)

A comprehensive pollution index method has been applied to evaluate water quality in many existing studies. The details of the comprehensive pollution index are shown below:

$$PI = 1/n \sum_{i=1}^n Ci/Si \quad (10)$$

Where,

PI = Comprehensive pollution index

Ci = Measured concentration of the pollutant (mg/L)

Si = Limits allowed by the WHO standard

n = Number of selected pollutants

Table 3: Loading values of the leading principal components of the selected variables in the Betkot Lake

Parameters	Components Matrix				
	1	2	3	4	5
EC	-0.20	0.90	-0.03	-0.09	0.10
TDS	-0.05	0.95	-0.02	-0.23	-0.01
DO	0.80	-0.46	0.17	0.25	0.14
TH	-0.09	0.35	0.01	0.12	0.89
K	0.33	0.05	0.81	-0.04	0.04
Na	-0.30	0.69	0.34	0.09	0.14
Ca	0.08	0.09	0.96	0.07	0.06
Mg	0.17	-0.16	0.31	0.90	0.08
NO3	0.41	-0.23	-0.32	0.76	0.09
PO4	0.24	-0.04	0.50	-0.33	0.69
NH4	0.04	-0.59	0.59	0.19	0.30
COD	-0.87	0.24	-0.32	-0.08	-0.16
BOD	-0.87	0.24	-0.32	-0.08	-0.16
Cl	0.76	0.22	-0.17	0.43	-0.24
Alkalinity	-0.31	0.33	-0.01	-0.23	-0.54
Eigenvalues	5.56	3.02	1.95	1.39	1.18
% of Variance	37.04	20.15	13.02	9.26	7.90
Cumulative %	37.04	57.19	70.21	79.47	87.37

Table 4: Standard of surface water quality classification Zhao et al. (2012)

COMPREHENSIVE POLLUTION INDEX (PI)	WATER QUALITY LEVEL
≤0.20	Cleanness
0.12-0.40	Sub-Cleanness
0.41-1.00	Slight Pollution
1.01-2.0	Moderate pollution
≥2.01	Severe pollution

The values of comprehensive Pollution Index (PI) of different sites are classified on the basis of Table 4 and are shown in Table 5. The values obtained from site 1-13 are 0.58, 0.59, 0.53, 0.51, 0.56, 0.53, 0.55, 0.53, 0.52, 0.54, 0.53, 0.59 and 0.59, respectively. The comprehensive PI showed that all the sites were slightly polluted (water quality classification; [\(Zhao et al., 2012\)](#)). The result showed that among all the sampling sites in the Betkot Lake, sites 2, 12 and 13 have the highest PI values whereas site 4 has the lowest. The concentrations of ammonia, pH, chloride, potassium was found to be higher with low DO than other sites this might be reason behind the highest PI values. Moreover, the PI values of sampling site 4 is lower i.e. 0.51, and possibly this lower value is due to the forest surrounding nearby the site. All these sites are characterized with the presence of high temperature, total hardness and free CO₂.

In order to confirm further the aforementioned results, the Cluster analysis dataset are used to calculate the PI (Table 6). The PI results are described on the basis of mean values of different chemical variables in the respective clusters. From the analysis of cluster results for the confirmation of the PI results all the clusters values have good agreement with the above results (Table 5) and it is quite comparable (Table 6). Cluster 1 formed by 7 out of 13 sampling sites indicated that the sites of this cluster has mostly retained its natural quality with little anthropogenic interference (PI= 0.54). Among the 4 clusters, the mean PI values were found highest in cluster 2, a location of sampling sites 1, 2 and 5. These sites lie near to the temple area and road structures. The PI outputs in both the cases found that the water quality level of the Betkot Lake was found to be slightly polluted. Thus, the cluster results are eventually used

to determine the PI values in comprehensive basis and revealed the good agreement with the results of single and comprehensive pollution index.

Table 5: Single and comprehensive pollution index of the Betkot Lake

S. N.	Parameters	Sampling sites												
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
		0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9		0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8
1	Tem.	5	4	3	3	2	3	9	2	0.9	9	6	8	8
		1.1	1.1			1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0		1.1	1.1	1.1	1.1
2	pH	3	1	1.1	1.1	9	9	6	9	1.1	2	3	6	5
		0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3		0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
3	EC	4	3	3	3	3	5	0.4	4	3	3	2	6	2
		0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3		0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
4	TDS	4	2	3	3	3	5	0.4	4	3	3	2	2	2
					0.5	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.5	0.6	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.6
5	DO	0.5	0.5	0.5	7	3	5	8	4	5	7	7	6	7
		1.5	1.4	1.6		1.4	1.5	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.4	1.4	1.6	0.1
6	TH	2	8	3	1.5	8	2	7	5	5	8	8	3	1
		0.6	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.6			0.6	0.6	0.6		0.5	0.0
7	CaH	2	1	5	1	1	0.6	0.6	7	6	2	0.6	8	1
		0.1		0.2	0.1		0.1		0.1	0.1		0.1	0.2	
8	MgH	1	0.1	3	1	0.1	3	0.2	2	4	0.1	1	1	0.8
		1.6	1.6		1.0	1.7	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.2	1.2	0.7	1.1	1.3
9	CO ₂	9	5	1.1	3	6	8	9	3	8	8	7	4	1

		0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4
10	K ⁺	3	3	3	3	4	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	2
		0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3
11	Na ⁺	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	9
		0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0
12	Ca ²⁺	7	6	5	6	8	6	6	7	6	2	6	6	3
		0.1	0.1		0.1	0.1	0.1		0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	
13	Mg ²⁺	4	3	0.1	4	3	6	0.1	5	7	2	4	5	0.1
		0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3
14	NO ₃ ⁻	3	3	3	3	3	5	1	3	7	5	3	5	2
		0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
15	PO ₄ ³⁻	7	7	7	7	7	6	7	7	7	6	6	7	7
		1.0	1.0	0.2	0.9	0.9		0.0	0.9	1.0	0.1	0.5	0.9	
16	NH ₄ ⁺	9	9	1	6	1	0.1	6	2	6	5	9	9	1.4
		1.7	1.9	2.0		1.6	2.2	2.3	1.4	1.0	2.2	2.2	2.2	1.8
17	COD	2	1	3	1.4	5	8	2	8	2	3	1	6	9
		0.9	1.0	1.1	0.7	0.9	1.2	1.2	0.8	0.5	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.0
18	BOD	6	6	3	8	2	7	9	2	6	4	3	5	2
		0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4
19	Cl ⁻	2	2	2	3	2	4	2	2	4	2	1	1	6
		0.1	0.1		0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
20	Alk	2	4	0.1	2	2	2	5	2	2	4	4	2	9
		0.5												
PI		8	9	3	1	6	3	5	3	2	4	3	9	9

Table 6: Comprehensive pollution index of water of the Betkot Lake on the basis of clustering of sampling sites

Cluster	Corresponding sites	Comprehensive pollution index (PI)	Water Quality Level (WQL)
1.	3, 4, 8, 9, 10, 11 & 13	0.54	Slight Pollution
2.	1, 2 & 5	0.58	Slight Pollution
3.	6, & 12	0.56	Slight Pollution
4.	7	0.55	Slight Pollution

4. Comparative Assessment of Water Quality

The comparison of the parameters with different lake and the pervious study is given in the Table 7. The pH value of the Betkot Lake is mildly alkaline and comparable with the majority of the lakes listed in Table 7 as well as the standard value. The mean EC measured during the study was 337 μ S/cm and it is higher than the past study result (224 μ S/cm ; Neupane et al., 2010). The observed data indicates that the mean EC value of the Betkot Lake is comparable with the Jagadispur reservoir (Table 7) and higher than the other selected lakes of this study. The observed mean TDS value in the lake is 168 mg/L which was relatively higher as compared to the previous studies, probably due to run off from the Churiya hills as well as various anthropogenic activities around the lake. Similarly, the chloride content in the Betkot Lake was comparable with the Jagadispur and Taudha Lakes. In the meantime, the present observation of the chloride contents in the lake is almost three times lower as compared to the results obtained from the Khaste Lake, Pokhara Metropolitan City (Table 7). The average total hardness recorded during analysis was 188 mg/L which is lower than the previous study of the same lake i.e. 271 mg/L (Neupane et al., 2010). Possibly, the domestic and animal wastes and other anthropogenic activities are responsible for the elevated, organic wastes in the lake; however, it is still lower in the Khaste Lake indicating less extent of natural and anthropogenic inputs. Free CO₂ in the Betkot Lake is comparable with the standard value (Table 7) and relatively lower than the other lakes.

Table 7: Comparison of physiochemical parameters mean value of present study with different lakes of Nepal

Lakes	pH	EC	TDS	Cl ⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	PO ₄ ⁻³	TH	DO	BOD	CO ₂	Reference
Betkot	7.70	337	168	12.20	0.06	0.50	188	3.00	31.80	7.33	Present study
Betkot	-	224	-	-	-	0.11	271	5.76	-	-	Neupane et al. (2010)
Jhilmila	-	177	-	-	-	0.16	43	6.80	-	-	Neupane et al. (2010)
Begnas	7.30	91	49	2.60	5.30	-	-	-	-	-	Khadka and Ramanathan (2013)
Jagadispur	6.90	379		9.70		0.28	-	7.30		25.80	Thapa and Saund (2012)
Nagdaha	7.80	195	106	27.10	1.64	0.21	68	7.10	11.40	31.70	Pant (2013)
Taudha	8.50	232	125	18.60	1.90	0.60	106	5.80	-	10.60	Pradhananga <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Nepalese	6.5-8.5	1500	1000	250	50	-	500	-	≤15	-	CBS (2019)
Standard											
WHO Standard	6.5-8.5	800-1000	500	250	-	0.80	80-120	4-6	-	6.00	WHO (2011)

The concentration of the phosphate is 0.07 mg/L but the previous study by Neupane et al. (2010) recorded higher value i.e., 0.11 mg/L. The concentration varied which may be due to the fluctuation on surface runoff, weathering of rocks, soil decay and mineralization of plants and animals remains. Concentration of nitrate is 0.06 mg/L; however, the concentrations of nitrate are dramatically higher in the Begnas Lake (Khadka and Ramanathan, 2013), which could be due to the high anthropogenic activities as it is one of the major touristic destination. The DO value of the Betkot Lake is found lowest in comparison with the other lakes, indicating relatively higher organic pollution in the lake, and it is even lower than the standard values may cause the adverse impacts to the aquatic biota. The previous study done by Neupane et al. (2010) recorded the high DO which was 5.00 mg/L and 5.76 mg/L. The high BOD value indicates more water pollution in the lentic environment. In the present study, the relatively low values of DO in the lake is an indicator of water pollution resulting the high value of BOD. It clearly reflects that the increasing organic pollution in the lake may cause serious problem in the future.

5. Conclusions

The Betkot Lake water has been using for multiple purposes and thus widely concerned for the local people and other stakeholders. Thirteen samples were collected from the lake and 21 hydrochemical variables are considered of the in-situ and laboratory analysis to evaluate the surface water quality of the lake. The major ions follow the order of $\text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$ for cations, and alkalinity $> \text{Cl}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{PO}_4^{3-}$ for anions. With the multivariate statistical methods, the significant hydrochemical factors on the spatial distribution of the surface water quality are analyzed like PCA and CA, and found useful in establishing and understanding the relation between water quality variables in the Betkot Lake. The spatial classifications are exactly consistent with the geographical locations of the sampling sites, and the water quality is better in the forest area and less disturbed sites whereas more polluted in the area having high anthropogenic interferences. Likewise, for the further confirmation of the CA results, the classification of the relatively polluted sites, the results of this research indicate that the CA technique is effective for offering the classifications of the freshwater quality of the lake environments. Similarly, the cumulative pollution index is applied and slightly pollution level was found in all the clustering sites of the lake. The PCA is used to identify a reduced number of five principal components, which demonstrated that 87.37% as spatial changes and showed the potential relationship among

the different hydrochemical variables. This study provides the detailed information on water quality of the Betkot Lake in comparison with other lakes. Also, the water quality in the lakes is found to be determined by natural and anthropogenic inputs. The status of ionic strength of lake is relatively low than other lakes, however due to anthropogenic inputs like more organic pollution and the rapid eutrophication process could be the serious threats and needs restoration of the lake. The findings of this study clearly demonstrate the status of the water quality in the lake are comparable and in agreement with the previous study of the same and other lakes in the country. The major measured chemical parameters were under the guidelines of WHO for drinking water and also mostly meet the guidelines of NWQGAC, however this also suggested that proper lake management is required to sustain the aquatic ecosystem. The finding from this study will be a supportive information for the development of effective management strategies in preventing and monitoring pollution levels in the lake. The results emphasized that Nepal should develop sustainable wetlands conservations strategies and water quality to protect aquatic biota as well as organisms including human beings.

In the nutshell, the finding of the research provides some insightful information for better improvement in the understanding of the relationships among various hydrochemical determinants and provide some guidance to the surface water quality monitoring and assessment of the other freshwater lakes around the country. Thus, the water quality of the lake environments needs to be further investigated focusing on the depth-wise and temporal levels.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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